

Coffee sensory properties: a complementary data fusion to simulate odour and taste integration by instrumental approach. Possibilities and limits

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Abstract

Coffee cupping includes both aroma and taste, and its evaluation considers several different attributes simultaneously to define flavour quality therefore requiring complementary data from aroma and taste. This study investigates the potential and limits of a data-driven approach to describe the sensory quality of coffee using complementary analytical techniques usually available in routinely quality control laboratory. Coffee flavour chemical data from 155 samples were obtained by analysing volatile (HS-SPME-GC-MS), and non-volatile (LC-UV/DAD) fractions, as well as from sensory data. Chemometric tools were used to explore the data sets, select relevant features, predict sensory scores and investigate the networks between features. A comparison of the Q model parameter and RMSEP highlights the variable influence that the non-volatile fraction has on prediction, showing that it has a higher impact on describing Acid, Bitter and Woody notes than on Flowery and Fruity. The data fusion emphasised the aroma contribution to driving sensory perceptions, although the correlative networks highlighted from the volatile and non-volatile data deserves a thorough investigation to verify the potential of odour-taste integration.

Keywords: coffee, LC-UV, HS-SPME-GC-MS, chemometrics, sensory data

Introduction

The characteristics and sensory properties of coffee flavour are unique and of high appeal for consumers [1]. The pleasure system includes different brain areas that are linked to emotional, memory-related, motivational and linguistic aspects of food evaluation that are, in turn, mediated by several sensory modalities and sub-modalities that contribute to flavour perception. The sensory panel therefore plays a fundamental role in this respect. The cupping protocol is however time-consuming, requires properly trained and aligned professional panellists, and may suffer from subjectivity. The ever-increasing consumption of coffee means that there is a need for analytical techniques to support the sensory panel in routine quality controls (QC) or formulation and design of new blends. Several analytical approaches and/or integrated strategies attempted, over the years, to combine the chemical composition of a product with its flavour profile [2, 3]; however, to date, they have not replaced a sensory panel evaluation, especially in regulatory contexts where sensory quality concurs to define labelling (e.g., extra-virgin olive oil) or a commercial value (e.g., coffee).

Issues related to their applicability might therefore be related to the attempt of reducing the extremely complex phenomenon of sensory perception, triggered by multiple ligands (volatiles and non-volatiles) and modulated by their cross-modal interactions, to a few correlations (e.g., reductionist approach) or to the adoption of spectroscopic/spectrometric technologies that have limited or not univocal “molecular resolution” [3]. Many research provides proof-of-evidence on the potential of applying omics workflows and concepts to identify “features patterns” (i.e. patterns of potential informative components) with high correlation to a biological output [2]. Moreover, machine learning applied to fingerprinting and/or profiling technologies highlighted strong relationships and networking between aroma and flavour. In this complex and intriguing scenario, starting by preliminary results obtained by applying omics principles to the modelling of specific coffee aroma notes, this study is a step forward in evaluating chromatographic fingerprints of volatile and non-volatile components as diagnostic signatures with strong correlation with selected taste and aroma attributes, i.e. bitterness, acidity, flowery, fruity, woody, and spicy. Moreover, fingerprinting is combined to machine learning, by partial least squares (PLS) algorithms, and extended to a comprehensive data matrix obtained by combining together peak features information deriving from volatiles and non-volatiles. PLS drives features selection toward those informative patterns capable of predicting sensory attributes and explaining correlations between them.

Experimental

Samples, consisting of roasted and ground coffees to suit a coffee-filter machine, were kindly supplied over a period of 24 months by Lavazza Spa (Turin, Italy). Mono-origin coffees from different countries were selected for

their distinctive and peculiar sensory notes, they accounted for a total of 155 samples belonging to *Coffea arabica* L. and *Coffea canephora* Pierre ex- A. Froehner species. Roasting degree was set at 55°Nh to be in line with the international standardization protocol for cupping (SCA protocol). The coffee brew for cupping and analysis was prepared from 18 g of coffee powder and 300 mL of water at 88-94°C with a commercially available coffee filter machine Xlong TSK-197A (Lavazza Spa, Turin, Italy).

Volatile fingerprints: HS-SPME GC-MS set up

Volatile fraction was evaluated by sampling 1.50 g of coffee powder by HS-SPME with a Polydimethylsiloxane/Divinylbenzene (PDMS/DVB) fibre of df 65 µm and 1 cm length from Merck (Bellefonte, PA, USA) at 50°C for 40 minutes, shaken at a constant speed. The internal standard was pre-loaded onto the fiber by sampling 5 µL of a 1000 mg/L solution of n-C13 in dibutylphthalate (DBP) at 50°C for 20 min a constant speed. Analysis was performed with a Shimadzu QP2010 GC-MS system equipped with Shimadzu GC-MS Solution 2.51 software (Shimadzu, Milan, Italy). Chromatographic conditions: T inj.: 250°C; inj. mode: splitless; carrier gas: helium at a flow rate of 1 mL/min. Capillary column: SGE SolGelwax (100% polyethylene glycol) 30 m x 0.25 mm dc x 0.25 µm df (Trajan Scientific and Medical, Melbourne, Australia). Temp. program, from 40°C (1 min) to 200°C at 3°C/min, then to 250°C (5 min) at 10°C/min. MS conditions: ionization mode: EI (70 eV); ion source: 200°C; transfer line: 250°C. Scan range: 35-350 m/z; scan speed 666 amu/sec.

Non-volatile fingerprints: LC-UV/DAD settings

Two millilitres of brew were filtered using a 0.2 µm 13 mm nylon membrane syringe filter (Agilent, Little Falls, DE, USA) and 20 µL were directly injected for LC-UV/DAD analysis. The non-volatile fraction was profiled by Agilent (model 1200), equipped with a Spectra System UV Diode Array Detector 1100 series (Agilent, Little Falls, DE, USA). Data acquisition were performed on Chemstation LC 3D software Rev 3.03 01-SR1 (Agilent, Little Falls, USA). The LC column was a Platinum EPS C18 (250×4.6 mm, 80A, 4 µm) (Alltech, Deerfield, USA).

Operation conditions: injection volume 20 µL; detection wavelength 325 nm for cinnamic and chlorogenic acids (monomers and dimers) and 276 nm for caffeine and trigonelline; mobile phase: A: water/formic acid (999:1, v/v) B: acetonitrile/formic acid (999:1, v/v); flow rate, 1.0 mL/min. The gradient program was as follows: 15% B for 7 min, 15-55% B in 20 min, 55-100% B in 25 min, 100% B for 2 min. Before re-injection, the LC system was stabilised for at least 5 min. Compounds identification, or tentative identification, was carried out on a LC-MS/MS Shimadzu Nexera X2 system equipped with a photodiode detector SPD-M20A connected, in series, to a triple quadrupole Shimadzu LCMS-8040 system equipped with an electrospray ionization (ESI) source (Shimadzu, Dusseldorf Germany).

Sensory analysis

Coffee sensory properties were evaluated by an external trained panel of six assessors both by sniffing the powder and the brew obtained using the filter method, and by tasting aspiring the beverage into the mouth. This multistep protocol allows panellists to evaluate different attributes, with some being more closely linked to aroma (odour notes like *flowery*, *fruity*, *woody* and *spicy*) and others more closely to taste (*acidity* and *bitterness*). The intensities of each attribute were evaluated simultaneously on a scale from 0 to 10.

Data elaboration

Data sets (Sensory scores, GC-MS and LC-UV/DAD fingerprints) were explored by Principal Component Analysis (PCA) followed by Multiple Factorial Analysis (MFA). Features selection for each data set, related to the sensory note, was performed using VIP>1 (variable importance in projection) from Partial Least Square-Discriminant Analysis (PLS-DA) on samples that were suitable to minimise and maximise the sensory notes expression. PLS regression was carried out on single perception modalities (i.e., aroma or taste) or flavour in toto by combining the two data set (i.e., volatiles and non-volatiles fingerprints). Data elaboration was performed using XLSTAT (version 2020.1.3 - copyright Addinsoft 2020). Raw analytical data representing the chromatographic fingerprints of volatiles and non-volatiles were pre-processed, as shown in the work-flow of (Figure 1A), via the temporal alignment of chromatograms and background noise subtraction. This pre-processing was made with Pirouette software ver. 4.5 (Infometrix, Inc., Bothell, WA, USA).

Results and discussion

Data exploration was, at first, performed using PCA on volatiles and non-volatile fingerprint features, treated independently. MFA was then used to compare the three different data matrices: chemical fingerprints (volatiles and non-volatiles) and the sensory data related to the sensory notes considered (Figure 1B) which shows how volatiles and non-volatiles for the different samples have quite similar branches, in a filtered group of samples (by origins) for better visualization, suggesting that there is a possible relationship between the different data matrices.

ethyl-2-methyl- and 2-ethylbutanoate, γ -decalactone, furfural and pentanoic acid, stating that odorants that enhance a target-taste perception may be exploited to modulate the overall taste perception in foods and beverages [4, 5].

Figure 2: A) PLS-regression models parameter for bitter, in validation and prediction, that were obtained using aroma and taste, singularly, and data fusion (flavour: volatiles + non-volatiles), B) comparison of the PLS parameters for four of the investigated notes. Models are built with specific selected features that were derived from PLS-DA analysis carried out on each sensory attribute.

Moreover, although to a different extent, in this work most of the identified tastants are positively correlated with volatiles related to *Bitter*. As flavour perception derives from the interaction between aroma and taste, the combination of the information provided by the two different fractions was expected to increase the performance of the predictive model.

The performance of the fused data matrix regression model was in line with those obtained using fingerprint data from volatile and non-volatile models. However, data fusion did not improve the overall prediction quality of the model (Q^2 figure 2A). Although the coffee non-volatile fraction analysed is not fully representative, nevertheless the considered non-volatile markers are well-established sensory quality marker in routine controls. The volatile fraction possibly has an actual influence in driving the description of this sensory attribute. This possibility, together with the correlation pathways between volatiles and non-volatiles, deserves much more in-depth investigation.

Conclusion

One major barrier to accurate predictions of flavour is due to the multi-dimensionality of the chemical stimuli involved in flavour perception. The fact of considering as many compounds as possible in the models takes care of possible correlations within and across stimuli, generally not accounted for by traditional research methods. There is an actual contribution to the multi-modal description for several attributes but the power in the definition of the sensory notes is negligible.

These observations, together with the good results obtained in the definition of *Bitter* and *Acid* notes (considered as “typical taste notes”) from the volatile data, make it possible to hypothesise that the analysis of the volatile fraction may be sufficiently representative to delineate coffee flavour, and provide reliable chemical fingerprints that can be associated to some sensory notes, including those typical of taste. Moreover, the correlative results highlighted from the volatile – non-volatile fused data deserves a thorough investigation to verify the potential of odour-taste integration.

References

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